

A Response to *Notes Métrologiques: Le Plancher de la Chambre du Roi à la Grande Pyramide* by L. Castaño Sánchez

Ian Douglas

ian@zti.co.za

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8452-7111>

Version 1.0.0

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6954734>

Licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence.

Unqid: fe03eec9d1b1cbede6dff6b38782380

Please check via DOI for latest version.

2 August 2022

Abstract

Luis Castaño Sánchez published a response[1] to my paper, *The King's Chamber Floor, decoded* [2]. This is my response to that, pointing out where I disagree with his objections, as well as critiquing his replacement Vitruvian Man model. In return, I offer some support for the mathematical cubit.

Keywords: Egyptology, Giza, Great Pyramid, History of Mathematics.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Summary of Mr Sánchez's points	2
3	My responses	2
3.1	Petrie and the King's Chamber dimensions	2
3.2	Anthropometric divisions of the cubit	2
3.3	Vitruvian Man	3
3.4	Dimensions of the floor blocks using 1.8 cm digits	5
4	Discussion and the mathematical cubit	6
5	Conclusion	8
6	Bibliography	8

1 Introduction

My paper, *The King's Chamber Floor, decoded* [2], analysed the blocks on the King's Chamber floor in the great pyramid. It showed that the blocks represented the usual Giza favourites, namely π , φ , e , $\sqrt{2}$, $\sqrt{3}$, $\sqrt{5}$, and c , amongst others. Mr Sánchez felt my analysis was misguided because I only used the royal cubit of 52.36 cm, and even worse, a decimal version, instead of his proposed system based on a cubit of 52.5 cm, divided into 30 digits of 1.8cm.

I do not read French, so I had to make the best of what Google Translate could do with his document.

There are several things about Mr Sánchez's system that I disagree with, discussed below.

There are many people investigating ancient Egypt in general, and Giza in particular, with an assortment of viewpoints and back-stories. I have seen many papers and opinions, and I sometimes wonder how they can think like that. No doubt many people feel the same about some of my opinions. I accept that people hold their views as a result of many hours of research. The problem is, you can make a simple mistake near the beginning, and then spend the rest of your life down the wrong rabbit hole because of that one

mistake, all the while believing your research to be correct, and getting frustrated with anyone who thinks differently. I hope I am not guilty of that.

Researchers have a lot invested in their chosen fields, and opinions about things that they have studied. In some ways, these beliefs that are deeply held become almost like a religion, and no one likes to have their views, developed over perhaps many years, challenged.

But that is exactly how the scientific process works... long-held ideas are challenged and eventually replaced as more and more people become convinced. Yet it is not pleasant for those who find their views out of favour.

“The language of Giza is mathematics.”

Robert Bauval

“You will believe.”

The architects of Giza

Changelog:

2022-07-30 1.0.0 Initial version

I use “cubit” for the Royal cubit (G).

2 Summary of Mr Sánchez’s points

If I understood his document correctly, Mr Sánchez’s makes the following main points in critiquing my paper:

1. He challenges the accepted dimensions of 20×10 G for the king’s chamber, saying that Petrie had no grounds to make that determination.
2. He says I probably have little or no knowledge of the anthropometric measurement system used in Egypt.
3. He then proposes that we should use the “Natural cubit = 6 palms = 45 cm”, where each digit is 1.8 cm. You no longer have 4 digits in a palm. He then brings in Vitruvian Man, the ideal man, being four natural cubits tall, or 4×45 cm = 180 cm.
4. He then provides revised measurements of the floor blocks using his 1.8 cm digits.

I shall respond to these in turn.

3 My responses

3.1 Petrie and the King’s Chamber dimensions

As far as I know, by the time Petrie went to Egypt [3], it was already accepted that the chamber was 20×10 G. The big debate at the time was around the value of the cubit, muddled by earlier explorers and analysts inventing Sacred Cubits and Pyramid Inches.

If the chamber is NOT meant to be 20×10 G, then what was the design intent? Everything about Giza and the great pyramid suggests careful mathematical design, even if the execution of that design was not always perfect. The 20×10 design leads to interesting mathematics, which is typical of the rest of Giza. I explore that in *Observations on the King’s Chamber Dimensions* [4].

Petrie used the 20×10 G dimensions to get what is arguably the best experimentally-determined value for the cubit, at 20.62 ± 0.004 [§ 52], later widened slightly to 20.62 ± 0.005 [§ 136]. This is not 0.5236 metres, but it is very close. See my paper *G1, c and G* [5] for a comparison of the different proposed cubit values.

3.2 Anthropometric divisions of the cubit

As regards the anthropometric divisions of the cubit, I am well aware of them. Indeed, my first published paper, *The Beautiful Cubit System* [6] analysed them in detail. I need to update that paper with what I have learned in the interim.

However, I have not seen these smaller cubit divisions used at Giza. There are also issues with their most commonly-cited use, that of the *seked*, for calculating pyramid slopes. For example, the slope of the Red pyramid can not easily be expressed in terms of these divisions [7].

Petrie was aware of the other cubit divisions, but barely mentions them in his entire book. In his chapter on the cubit, he only mentions the digit, and queries the 28 digits per cubit idea. He mentions “palm” once (page 74), “span” once when quoting an earlier writer, but not “hand” (as length), “fist”, or *remen*.

I don't have a problem with 28 digits in the cubit, but neither have I seen evidence for their use thus far.

3.3 Vitruvian Man

Regarding Mr Sánchez's general “ideal man” proposal:

Firstly, it is not the case that the royal cubit is the short cubit plus another palm. Rather, the royal cubit came first, and the short cubit is a royal cubit minus a palm.

Secondly, men in dynastic Egypt were much shorter than 1.8 metres tall on average.

“The average height of the male population varied between 161 cm (5.28 feet) in the New Kingdom (about 1550–1070 BC) and 169.6 cm (5.56 feet) in the Early Dynastic period (about 2925–2575 BC), making an average of 165.7 cm (5.43 feet) for all time periods.” [8]

Even today, with the benefits of modern nutrition and health-care, apart from one spot in central Africa, it is only among the Germanic tribes of northern and eastern Europe that we find men averaging around 1.8 metres tall [9]. So claiming that dynastic Egyptians used this height as an “ideal standard” does not make sense.

Further, while other cubits around the middle east may have been divided into 30 digits, I don't know of any Egyptian royal cubits that are divided like that. Our best examples are divided into 28 digits.

In my opinion, the whole system relating cubit divisions to body parts was a matter of convenient names, rather than being based on the actual body part dimensions, as I shall now illustrate.

I made a modern cubit rod, the design is shown in Figure 1. The rod is 52.36 cm long, and each digit is 1.87 cm. There is a cm scale at the top, and cubit divisions at the bottom.

The actual rod is shown in Figure 2. Apologies for the camera flash.

The size of your hands and fingers are related to your height. Taller people have bigger hands. Further, it is also related to your body type [10]. Endomorphs will generally have wider and meatier hands and fingers than Ectomorphs. I am about 1.73 metres tall, and an ectomorph, but even my finger is wider than a digit. Figure 3 shows my left index finger on my cubit rod. You can see the 3 digit marker on the right of the finger, but the 2 digit marker is under the finger. The finger was lightly resting on the ruler, not squashed flat. The doubled text is the shadow.

My “palm” measurement is also wider than a palm, which on my cubit rod is 4 digits, or 7.48 cm, as shown in Figure 4.

A person who is 1.8 metres tall would have wider fingers and hands than me, especially if they were also an endomorph. So clearly the “theory” does not stand up to the reality.

Leonardo DaVinci had to “cheat” [11] to get his Vitruvian Man design to work: “Leonardo did not represent Vitruvius's proportions of the limbs but rather included those he found himself after measuring male models in Milan.” [12]. Human dimensions do not match Vitruvius's “ideal” design.

Ates Gulcugi shows that using a seven-division grid rather than a six-division grid produces better results for analysing Vitruvian Man [13].

I have not seen evidence for the short cubit being used at Giza. The only unit I have found for large scale measurements is the cubit. Occasionally, converting a length to metres produces interesting results, but it is clear that they used cubits as the tool of choice. For smaller measurements, it is becoming increasingly clear that they used a decimal cubit divided into 100 centicubits and 1000 millicubits, rather than the expected digits, palms, etc.

Fig. 5 shows how part of such a decimal cubit rod might look, compared to a metric ruler. For some reason, it shrinks from true size when printed.

Figure 3: The digit

Figure 4: The palm

Figure 5: Centimetres and millimetres compared to decimal centicubit and millicubit divisions.

This raises the question of “why 28 digits” then? I am investigating a possible use case for such cubit divisions.

3.4 Dimensions of the floor blocks using 1.8 cm digits

Mr Sánchez’s then produces a map of the king’s chamber floor, shown in a video by Nicolas Vantyghem [14]. The video is dated 23 July 2021. I downloaded a version of that diagram on 26 February 2021 from a Russian website, which neither Google Image Search nor Yandex can now find, shown in Figure 6. The search engines only find a modified version on a blog.

Figure 6 appears to be a metricated version to the nearest millimetre of a diagram posted by Bernard Pietsch in 2004 [15], shown in Figure 7. You will observe that the dimensions in Figure 7 have long strings of decimals. That is because they are not the actual measurements, but have been scaled by 1.01430555, to fit in with Pietsch’s solar system model [16]. So the starting point for Mr Sánchez’s dimensions is not based on actual measurements.

would otherwise be infinite strings of decimals.

I make no apologies for the metre. I don't know how or why they knew the length, but things "just work" when using it. So it is another strong circumstantial indicator that Giza is not fourth dynasty.

Name	Symbol	Practical value in metres
Archimedes' constant	π	3.1416
Euler's number	e	2.7183
e^{-1}	\acute{e}	1.7183
Golden ratio	φ	1.618
Golden ratio squared	φ^2	2.618
metre	m	1
Royal cubit	\mathbb{C}	0.5236
foot = m/\acute{e}	F	0.3047 or 0.30472
megalithic yard = $\mathbb{C} + F$	Y	0.8283
grand metre = $m + \mathbb{C}$	M	1.5236 (5 feet)
six feet = $m + \mathbb{C} + F$	S	1.8283

Table 1: Symbols, names and values

I am aware that the so-called "megalithic yard" is controversial. I have not found it used at Giza. However, it does slot into the series shown below, and is a cubit plus foot in this version.

It looks like lengths got longer over time, for example

- The foot went from 0.30472 to 0.3048
- The cubit went from 0.5236 to 0.5250
- The megalithic yard went from 0.8283 to 0.829056 (based on 32.64" [20])

The cubit comes from a circle with one metre diameter, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: The origin of $\pi/6$

Then, correct to 4 decimals,

$$\text{digit} = \frac{\pi}{168} = \frac{\varphi^2}{140} = \frac{\pi\varphi}{100e} = 0.0187$$

$$28 \times 0.0187 = 0.5236 = \mathbb{C}$$

and

$$\mathbb{C} = \pi - \varphi^2 = \frac{\varphi^2}{5} = \frac{\pi}{6} = \frac{\varphi^2 + \pi}{5 + 6} = \frac{2\pi - \varphi^2}{7} = \frac{5\varphi e}{6 \cdot 7} = \frac{7\varphi\pi}{5^2 e} = \left(\frac{\varphi + 1}{e - 1} - 1 \right) = \left(\frac{\pi + 1}{e} - 1 \right) = 0.5236$$

and

$$M = 1 + \mathbb{C} = \frac{1 + \pi}{e} = \frac{\varphi^2}{\acute{e}} \left(= \frac{\varphi + 1}{e - 1} \right) = \pi - \varphi = 1.5236$$

and

$$\frac{\mathbb{G}}{\mathbb{F}} = \frac{e\mathbb{G}}{\mathbb{Y}} = \frac{\acute{e}}{\mathbb{m}} = \frac{\varphi^2}{\mathbb{M}} = \frac{\pi}{\mathbb{S}} = 1.7183 \quad (= e - 1)$$

The cubit can be elegantly divided into the various parts using π , τ , or φ^2 . Table 2 shows how to do it using π and τ , with a digit of $\pi/168$ or $\tau/336$. Table 3 shows the φ^2 method, using a digit of $\varphi^2/140$, or a palm of $\varphi^2/35$. There are two versions of the remen, one based on 20 digits, and the other being half the diagonal of a one-cubit square.

Note how $\pi/7$ gives the short cubit, and $\varphi^2/7$ gives the 20-digit remen.

Digits	Name	Formula π	Formula τ	Value m
1	Digit	$\frac{1\pi}{168}$	$\frac{\tau}{336}$	0.0187
4	Palm	$\frac{4\pi}{168}$	$\frac{4\tau}{336}$	0.0748
5	Hand	$\frac{5\pi}{168}$	$\frac{5\tau}{336}$	0.0935
6	Fist	$\frac{6\pi}{168}$	$\frac{6\tau}{336}$	0.1122
8	Double Palm	$\frac{8\pi}{168}$	$\frac{8\tau}{336}$	0.1496
12	Small span	$\frac{12\pi}{168}$	$\frac{12\tau}{336}$	0.2244
14	Great span	$\frac{14\pi}{168}$	$\frac{14\tau}{336}$	0.2618
16	Foot	$\frac{16\pi}{168}$	$\frac{16\tau}{336}$	0.2992
	Remen ($\sqrt{2}$)	$\frac{\pi}{6\sqrt{2}} = \frac{\mathbb{G}}{\sqrt{2}}$	$\frac{\tau}{12\sqrt{2}}$	0.3702
20	Remen	$\frac{20\pi}{168}$	$\frac{20\tau}{336}$	0.3740
24	Cubit (short) \mathbb{C}	$\frac{24\pi}{168} = \frac{\pi}{7}$	$\frac{24\tau}{336}$	0.4488
28	Cubit (royal) \mathbb{C}	$\frac{28\pi}{168} = \frac{\pi}{6}$	$\frac{28\tau}{336}$	0.5236
32	Pole	$\frac{32\pi}{168}$	$\frac{32\tau}{336}$	0.5984
36	Nby-rod	$\frac{36\pi}{168}$	$\frac{36\tau}{336}$	0.6732
64	Double pole	$\frac{64\pi}{168}$	$\frac{64\tau}{336}$	1.1968

Table 2: Divisions of the cubit using π and τ

5 Conclusion

I doubt I have convinced Mr Sánchez to change his mind, but perhaps I have shown enough to give him something to think about. There are many things about Egyptian history in general, and Giza in particular, that do not make sense, and it is only when we think outside the box of the conventional narrative that we can start to untangle the mysteries and find the truth of our past.

6 Bibliography

- [1] L. C. Sánchez, “NOTES MÉTROLOGIQUES: LE PLANCHER DE LA CHAMBRE DU ROI À LA GRANDE PYRAMIDE.”, [Online]. Available: https://www.academia.edu/83671180/NOTES_M%C3%89TROLOGIQUES_LE_PLANCHER_DE_LA_CHAMBRE_DU_ROI_%C3%80_LA_GRANDE_PYRAMIDE (visited on 2022-07-31).
- [2] I. Douglas, “The King’s Chamber Floor, decoded”, Zenodo, 2022-07-20. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6866853. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/6866853> (visited on 2022-07-24).
- [3] W. M. F. (M. F. Petrie, *The Pyramids and Temples of Gizeh*, in collab. with Cornell University Library. London : Field & Tuer ; New York : Scribner & Welford, 1883, 315 pp. [Online]. Available: <http://archive.org/details/cu31924012038927> (visited on 2021-09-18).
- [4] I. Douglas, “Observations on the King’s Chamber Dimensions”, 2022-07-30. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6944186. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/6944187> (visited on 2022-07-30).
- [5] —, “G1, c and \mathbb{C} : Khufu’s pyramid, the speed of light, and the royal cubit, compared”, Zenodo, 2022-07-25. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6900645. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/6900645> (visited on 2022-07-31).

Digits	Name	Formula digit	Formula palm	Value m
1	Digit	$\frac{1\varphi^2}{140}$	$\frac{0.25\varphi^2}{35}$	0.0187
4	Palm	$\frac{4\varphi^2}{140}$	$\frac{1\varphi^2}{35}$	0.0748
5	Hand	$\frac{5\varphi^2}{140}$	$\frac{1.25\varphi^2}{35}$	0.0935
6	Fist	$\frac{6\varphi^2}{140}$	$\frac{1.5\varphi^2}{35}$	0.1122
8	Double Palm	$\frac{8\varphi^2}{140}$	$\frac{2\varphi^2}{35}$	0.1496
12	Small span	$\frac{12\varphi^2}{140}$	$\frac{3\varphi^2}{35}$	0.2244
14	Great span	$\frac{14\varphi^2}{140}$	$\frac{3.5\varphi^2}{35}$	0.2618
16	Foot	$\frac{16\varphi^2}{140}$	$\frac{4\varphi^2}{35}$	0.2992
	Remen ($\sqrt{2}$)	$\frac{\varphi^2}{5\sqrt{2}}$		0.3702
20	Remen	$\frac{20\varphi^2}{140} = \frac{\varphi^2}{7}$	$\frac{5\varphi^2}{35}$	0.3740
24	Cubit (short) C	$\frac{24\varphi^2}{140}$	$\frac{6\varphi^2}{35}$	0.4488
28	Cubit (royal) G	$\frac{28\varphi^2}{140} = \frac{\varphi^2}{5}$	$\frac{7\varphi^2}{35}$	0.5236
32	Pole	$\frac{32\varphi^2}{140}$	$\frac{8\varphi^2}{35}$	0.5984
36	Nby-rod	$\frac{36\varphi^2}{140}$	$\frac{9\varphi^2}{35}$	0.6732
64	Double pole	$\frac{64\varphi^2}{140}$	$\frac{16\varphi^2}{35}$	1.1968

Table 3: Divisions of the cubit using φ^2

- [6] Douglas, Ian, *The Beautiful Cubit System*, 2019-06-30. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3263864>.
- [7] “Sekeds and the Geometry of the Egyptian Pyramids”. (), [Online]. Available: <http://www.davidfurlong.co.uk/sekes0.htm> (visited on 2022-07-30).
- [8] R. Lorenzi. “Mummies’ Height Reveals Incest”, Seeker. (2015-05-11), [Online]. Available: <https://www.seeker.com/mummies-height-reveals-incest-1769829336.html> (visited on 2019-06-25).
- [9] D. World. “Height Chart of Men and Women in Different Countries”, Disabled World. (2017-12-01), [Online]. Available: <https://www.disabled-world.com/calculators-charts/height-chart.php> (visited on 2022-07-30).
- [10] “THE 3 SOMATOTYPES”. (), [Online]. Available: https://www.uh.edu/fitness/comm_educators/3_somatotypesNEW.htm (visited on 2022-07-30).
- [11] L. Martin-Santos. “Da Vinci was wrong”, Medium. (2018-10-31), [Online]. Available: <https://medium.com/@lmartinsantos/da-vinci-was-wrong-65ca0776d774> (visited on 2022-07-30).
- [12] Vitruvian Man, in *Wikipedia*, 2022-07-26. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Vitruvian_Man&oldid=1100593699 (visited on 2022-07-30).
- [13] U. Gulcugil, “Vitruvian Man, 180 or 210?”, 2020-05-23.
- [14] Histoire de Pyramides, director, *PYRAMIDE DE KHÉOPS – Enquête sur la chambre haute et les chambres dites de décharge #6*, 2021-07-23. [Online]. Available: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oPhPOeG-8m4> (visited on 2022-07-31).
- [15] “King’s Chamber Floor Diagram”. (), [Online]. Available: <http://www.sonic.net/bernard/kc-floor.html> (visited on 2022-07-30).
- [16] “Anatomy of the of the King’s Chamber - Cheops’ Pyramid”. (), [Online]. Available: <http://www.sonic.net/bernard/kings-chamber.html> (visited on 2022-07-30).
- [17] *Cubit*, in *Wikipedia*, 2022-07-25. [Online]. Available: <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Cubit&oldid=1100437101> (visited on 2022-08-01).
- [18] I. Douglas, “Zep Tepi Mathematics 101”, Zenodo, 2021-01-16. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4410650. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4410650> (visited on 2021-09-18).
- [19] —, “Pahl’s Point and the Giza Star Map | Zenodo”. (), [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/6794297> (visited on 2022-07-04).
- [20] R. Hicks, “Thom’s Megalithic Yard and Traditional Measurements”, *Irish Archaeological Research Forum*, vol. 4, pp. 1–7, 1977-01-01. DOI: 10.2307/20495250.